

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsALFIYA S bearing USN 6SU21CC001 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsANSIF AK bearing USN 6SU21CC002 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsFAJID MOHAMMED bearing USN 6SU21CC003has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsFAWAS K BASHEER bearing USN 6SU21CC004has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsGOPIKA VINOJ bearing USN 6SU21CC005has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOURIKRISHNA. S bearing USN 6SU21CC006 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsINDRAJITH M bearing USN 6SU21CC007has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED BASITH C H bearing USN 6SU21CC008 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED BILLAL BIN JAMAL bearing USN 6SU21CC009 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAYANTHARA RAJI bearing USN 6SU21CC010 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSALMATHUL MISIRIA K A bearing USN 6SU21CC011 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSANGEETH M SHAJI bearing USN 6SU21CC012 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSHERVEN SAJI bearing USN 6SU21CC013 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSHIFA THAHSIN bearing USN 6SU21CC014has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VEEKSHITHA POOJARY bearing USN 6SU21CC015 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsARIYA PRAKASH bearing USN 6SU21CC016has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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